

Postmodernism: Concepts and Techniques

Rgwan Abdalhameed Shuash, Seriaznita Binti Said, Malik Oufi Jasim Al-Maliki, Al-Fartoosi Rana Ali Mhoodar

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Abstract

Postmodernism refers to all forms of representation as well as the new ways of depiction. This depiction refers to what is called reality and truth. These forms of representation rely upon narrative in order to validate themselves. Within this depiction, representations of art and culture demand some meta-narrative to be explained, validated or justified. The emphasis of literary postmodernism had the tendency as form of writing, which is the narrative fiction. Within postmodernism, there is a tendency that accepts literature as intrinsically narrative. This paper examines the use of postmodern techniques as a characteristic feature of this literary era. Concept(s) such as discourse, and masculine/feminine. Techniques are such as irony, black humour, playfulness, parody, pastiche, temporal distortion, paranoia, transformation, minimalism, maximalism, fragmentation, metafiction, reflexiveness and self-parody, symbolism and self-conscious narrators, stream of consciousness.

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Introduction

Roundly in 1997, (Frow)John Frowstated that the word“postmodernism” “can be taken as nothing more and nothing less than a genre of theoretical writing.The postmodern appeared as a form of a fog of discourse, which was highlighted more noticeably than what it was understood to be concerned with. Thus, the passing of postmodernism from the stage of growth into its more autonomous phase. consequently, postmodernism had become an entire climate, more than a form of cultural barometer(pp.,4).

During the third phase of postmodernism in the 1990s, it achieved its generalizability. Therefore, the force of postmodernism as an ideal appears to have started to dissolve. In a possible way, the acceptance of the widespread postmodern conditions existed in society, culture, and politics. And even a postmodern organization in arts and culture lead to show its difficulty to see postmodernism as an invention. The kind of presentation that is found in postmodernism is common with modernism. While in the past, other literary periods have taken place as cultures have looked elsewhere. This look is characterized with a restarting attention to other periods such as the Renaissance and antiquity, Romanticism with its native archaisms and exoticisms. Even modernism with its strange mix of primitivism and contemporaneity. On the contrary, postmodernism is all about exclusiveness with the nature of its own presentness. In fact, postmodernism is defined as the condition in which for the first time, and as a result of technologies that allow large-scale storage, access, and reproduction of records of the past, the past appears to be included in the present, or at the present's disposal, and in which the ratio between present and past has therefore changed (Connor, 2004).

The English expression ‘post-modern’ as found by Welsch was first used around 1870 by the English painter John Watkins Chapman who tried to go beyond French impressionism. A different meaning was attributed to the polysemic signifier (i.e. multiple meanings) in 1917 by Rudolf Pannwitz (1881–1969), a writer and philosopher, who saw man as a being capable of ‘completing the cosmos’. Then, the follows Nietzsche demanded a postmodern effort to overcome nihilism and decadence by ‘superman’. While the question of subjectivity and identity from romanticism and realism was inherited in the late modernism (from Shelley, George Eliot, Balzac), the question becomes marginal in postmodernism and is often old-fashioned by the question about reality as environment. (Zima, 2010, pp.,8-13).

Postmodern is “a notoriously difficult and contested term that, for its opponents, signals the twentieth century’s abandonment of truth and reason in favor of a world that is known only through images, signs or copies. For its defenders the postmodern is a liberating attitude that remains suspicious of any single foundation or ultimate position of truth” (Claire, 2004, p.182). Clearly, the subjection of postmodernism for argument among many highly praised theorists is of great significance such as the disreputable declaration of Jean Baudrillard that the Gulf War did not occur as well as the debate of both Fredric Jameson and Linda Hutcheon on whether parody can be looked at as postmodern (Wood & Lodge, 2014).

During the 1870s, Postmodern as a notion was first used. Meanwhile, suggestion by John Watkins Chapman that a postmodern style of painting is as a way to move beyond French Impressionism. In *The Hibbert Journal*, as a critique of religion, (Scotland, Paul, Thompson, & Stevenson, 1914, p.733) described changes in attitudes and beliefs as, “The raison d’être – the reason of existence – of Post-Modernism is to escape from the double-mindedness of Modernism by being thorough in its criticism by extending it to religion as well as theology, to Catholic feeling as well as to Catholic tradition”.

Cova (1996, p.15) describes postmodernism as the merging of the newly appeared models into a “generic perspective on life and the human condition” and an era of running from modernity and escaping the rational thinking. In addition, postmodernism declines the epistemological suppositions, disproves theories of acceptance, as well as opposes modernist realities in every sense. The emphasis of postmodernism is on describing an exhausted epoch of a common ideology, which is overfilled with paradoxes, and diversity of styles and juxtaposed assumptions as well.

Concepts of Postmodernism

One of the most significant concepts of postmodernism is discourse, which represents the use of language through communication in which structures are formed and meanings are conveyed as well (Holtzhausen, 2002). On one hand, language and culture are criticized by postmodernism critics as it spreads the way of critical thinking, which is used for achieving greater political autonomy. On the other hand, critical theory depicts the way media moves not only for entertaining but rather for forming how society thinks about the world. Media, according to Mickey (1997, p.272) is “a consciousness industry”.

Feminist writers are using deconstructionist techniques for analysing patriarchal discourse where sexual difference, personified in the concept of masculine/feminine (Scott, 1988). A kind of “progress” as Foucault believes is exhibited in the modern era in the dissemination and refinement of techniques of domination. He is similar to that of Weber, who analysed rationalization as a process of refining means of domination (Butler, 2002, pp.,28). Similarly, in *The History of Sexuality* (1980b), Foucault attempts to write the history of the “polymorphous techniques of power” that have inscribed the body within discourses of sexuality which have a powerful “normalizing” influence. (Foucault, 1980, pp.,36).

Techniques of Postmodernism

Linda Hutcheon (1986) claims that postmodern fiction, in general, could be described as having its ironic quote marks in such a way that it could be considered as tongue-in-cheek/sarcastic. Irony, black humours and playfulness are among the most recognisable themes and techniques of postmodernism. In studying postmodern literature, much of the focus is on intertextuality as a decentered perspective of the universe. Intertextuality is the way one text of literature is related to another one. This point is indicated to as lack of originality of postmodernism as well as its reliance on clichés. The complication in this perspective is more than a single reference to another text. For instance, Robert Coover’s *Pinocchio in Venice* links Pinocchio to Thomas Mann’s *Death in Venice* (Orr & Rodopi, 2009). In this regard, (Sharma & Chaudhary, 2011) have said that postmodern literature, refers to postmodernism in general.

Irony: In “*The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Literary Terms*” (Baldick, 1996, pp.,130) defines Irony as “a subtly humorous perception of inconsistency, in which an apparently straightforward statement or event is undermined by its context so as to give it a very different significance”. Dramatic irony is a literary term “in which the audience knows more about a character’s situation than the character does, foreseeing an outcome contrary to the character’s expectations, and thus ascribes a sharply different sense to some of the character’s own statements” while verbal irony “involves a discrepancy between what is said and what is really meant” (Baldick, 1996, pp.,141).

In feminist fictions, both of parody and irony become main kinds of formal and ideological critique. Speaking of the effectiveness of parody in her book, *The Canadian Postmodern* Linda Hutcheon says that the irony and distance implied by parody allow to split the doubled structure of both. Within parody, there is both the assertion and undercutting, which it contests (Hutcheon, 1988, pp.,7).

Pastiche is a French word borrowed into English during the 1880s and 1890s. Pastiche means “a work of art imitating another author’s style” (Tran-Gervat, 2014, pp.,1). This word is originally derived from the Italian pasticcio, meaning (from late Latin antiquity) a kind of mixed pastry (Attardo, 2014). Pastiche is the combination of multiple elements, which are related to postmodern intertextuality. It can represent aspects of chaos or plurality of postmodern society. Furthermore, it can combine multiple genres to comment on situations in postmodernity. An example of that is the use of science fiction by William S. Burroughs. Moreover, a compositional technique is also involved in it, for example, the cut-up technique employed by Burroughs (Barry, 2002).

Temporal distortion is used in postmodern fiction in a number of ways and takes a variety of forms, which range from fractured narratives to games with cyclical, mythical or spiral time. Temporal distortion is employed to create various effects: irony, parody, a cinematographic effect, and the effect of computer games. In postmodernism, it is said that change is essential and flow is normal, therefore, time is given as a construction to the representation of time in Kurt Vonnegut’s prose. Here the writer emphasizes the idea of time, and changes

of time are a distinctive feature of his literary work (Fedosova, 2015). Rosen (2001) has compared modern temporality to a battlefield saying that modern temporality is similar to a battle terrain in which a disarranging force of time struggles to control and manage time. Therefore, authors emphasize the necessity of personal experience of time.

Paranoia, or the threat of total engulfment by somebody else's system" (Lewis 129) is the belief that there's an ordering system behind the bedlam of the universe. The term is a thought process which is influenced by anxiety and fear. Paranoia thinking includes tormented attitude because the person believes he is in danger or is threatened by something or someone. In *Top Girls*, the sense of paranoia is demonstrated by the character of Angie. She shows that she fears darkness.

The technique of transformation is also a key technique in postmodern drama and is used by Churchill in *The Skriker* (1994). The one-act play tells the story of an ancient fairy that transforms into different objects like a sofa and to people like a nurse in the asylum, Lily's own mother, and a seductive stranger. The fairy chases Lily and Josie, two teenage mothers whom it befriends, manipulates, seduces and entraps. (Rabillard, 2009, pp., 102) claims that "in *The Skriker* human aggression was projected onto the natural world which was transformed into a damaged, poisoned, devious enemy combatant" (102).

Fragmentation is used by postmodern writer to alter the traditional elements such as narrative, plot, character, and setting of the literary work. (Lewis, 2001, pp., 127) describes fragmentation as "breaking up the text into short fragments or sections, separated by space, titles, numbers or symbols". Fragmentation is present in *The Skriker* as the events of Scene One take place in the Underworld, Scene Two takes place in a Mental Hospital, and Scene Three takes place in A Street, Scene Four in A Pub, scene Five in A Street, scene Six in A Room, scene Seven in A Park, scene Seven in the Underworld, scene Eight and scene Nine in A Park, scene Ten is A Room, scene Eleven in A Kitchen, scene Twelve in A Room, scene Thirteen in A Mental Hospital and scene Fourteen in A Dark Place, a hundred years later.

It has been agreed that metafiction as a term has been used ever since by the American novelist and critic Gass (1971, pp., 1) in his book *Fiction and the Figures of Life* describing John Barth's the fiction and Flann O'Brien's as well, he writes, "Indeed, many of the so-called antinovels are really metafiction." (Waugh, 1984) in her book about *Metafiction: The Theory and Practice of Self-Conscious Fiction* comments that "is more responsible than any other for the prominence of the term in the Anglo-American critical lexicon" (Fang, 2006). Waugh has defined Metafiction as a term used in fictional writing in which attention is drawn to question the relationship between fiction and reality (Waugh, 1993). There is a tendency that Metafiction stresses the fact that reality is constructed through linguistic structures of texts. Metafiction is used to emphasize its status as fiction. Therefore, it is more a formal term than a historical one (McCaffery, 1986). Artificiality of art is made obvious to the reader with disregarding the necessity for willing suspension of disbelief. For instance, as dictated by postmodern sensibility and metafiction, there should be a parody for parody itself by works of parody (Ayala & Bernabe, 2009; Luttazzi, 2004).

In Vonnegut's novel *Timequake*, as the title suggests, is the author's term, which is full of variations of changes in time. The title covers the idea of hesitation of a current of time. The preface of the novel presents the definition of 'a timequake' is given: '... a timequake, a sudden glitch in the space-time continuum ...' (Vonnegut, 1998, pp., 10). The author presents two story lines that intertwine. In 2001 Traut is a writer of recognition who has arrived at the conference, and in 2010 he is a person without any means of livelihood. Temporal Distortion is used in postmodern fiction in which fragmentation and non-linear narratives are central. In many cases, the use of this technique in postmodern fiction is in a variety of ways to create irony. It is also presented in historiographic metafiction, the best example is Billy Pilgrim as a main character in *Slaughterhouse-Five*. (Barry, 2002).

The belief that even chaos has an ordering system behind it, which is another postmodern theme. This means that no dependence of ordering upon the subject. Therefore, paranoia overlays the line between delusion and brilliant insight. Pynchon's *The Crying of Lot 49* is regarded a prototype of postmodern literature, in which a case is like coincidence or conspiracy (Pynchon, 1986).

Critics such as Newman (1987) and Stevenson (1985) comment that minimalism and postmodernism are like two eggs in the same basket. While other critics such as Herzinger (1985) has added to the comparison saying that the minimalist postmodernist connection to consist in the suspicion of traditional notions of historicity. The technique of minimalism emphasizes the surface description where the expectation that readers tend to have a role of activity in forming a story. It represents the basic pieces, specific by the economic use of words. As a minimalist author, he/she hesitates to use adjectives, adverbs, or meaningless details. However, a general context is provided by an author and then the reader will be allowed to shape the story imaginatively (Klarer, 2013).

The work of Borges has shown in stories "techniques of reflexivity and self-parody suggest a universe in which human consciousness is incapable of transcending its own mythologies" (Graff, 1979, pp., 56). To return to the Postmodern *Weltanschauung*, (German, from world perception). It shows Alan Wilde's contributions to the debate of postmodern. Wilde expands the concept of Postmodernist literature as he has

included writers such as Max Apple and Stanley Elkin in his postmodern standard. As a fact, it is obvious that these writers have participated too much for most compelling postmodern fictions. (Natoli & Hutcheon, 1993, pp.,60).

There has been an agreement among most critics that the matter of literary technique, important continuities between Modernism and Postmodernism. However, there exist other differences, such as the changing role of the reader in the postmodern "loss of self." As for the role of the reader, as (Hoffmann, Hornung, & Kunow, 1977, pp.,40) put it: "From a communicational point of view, modernism seems to stress the relationship between the creative sensibility and the work of art, between addresser and message, postmodernism that between message and addressee". (Holland, 1983, pp.,295) agrees with this: "In general, Postmodern criticism has turned decisively to the relation between reader and text".

The processes of signification are taken by the sign-reflective techniques of writing, that diverts the attention away from story. In a typical manner, textual play of forms, plots and tropes are emphasized as well as they mediate the relationship to the real to the signified. This form of writing is a medium particularly suited to the complex task of probing the relationship between language and meaning. (Natoli & Hutcheon, 1993, pp.,534).

The demand of female Prometheus is one of the major themes in feminist theory on both sides for the past decade. Such demand has been that of hat women writers like in Claudine Hermann's phrase "thieves of language" (Kottiswari, 2008, pp.,7). Grace has controlled a dialogic relationship between a realistic, a fantastic, and a poetic literary discourse. These have been parallel to the central theme in the novel, the dialogue between the self and the self as other. There has been an exclusion from the dominant cultural order, which has been situated outside rational discourse. (Kottiswari, 2008, pp.,46). In the novels of Hurston, the major themes that have emerged, were the black woman's search for self-fulfilment through community. Also, their quest for the ideal relationship between man and woman. In addition to black sisterhood and significance of fidelity in interpersonal relationships.

Atwood, as using devices such as irony, symbolism and self-conscious narrators, she shows a great talent in using of postmodern techniques for exploring the relationship between humanity and nature. Then the dark side of human behavior and power because it is related to gender and politics. Atwood has also given a definition to the goals of contemporary Canadian literature gaining a notable reputation among feminist writers as being exploring women's issues. Toni Morrison has used the technique of the Mirror point out the split within her female Protagonists. The technique has become a symbol of the split self and one's own reflection functions like a kind of negative double. It is apparent that the mirror gives a distorted image of the self, one that is robbed of an identity. Using the technique of third person narration instead of the first-person monologue. Irony is used to split the spatial and temporal dimensions within consciousness (Kottiswari, 2008, pp.,11-26).

The stream-of-consciousness is another technique used by Toni Morrison through the minds of various characters as a slow recreation of the past, both individually and communally. Hariharan uses the technique of disuniting patriarchal structures, which is similar to what Salman Rushdie does in all his novels. From a poststructuralist perspective, Rushdie has read the Indian political scene and adapted certain strategies of the post-modernist novel and created a new technique for his fiction. With flashback and stream-of-consciousness techniques, Bai's story gets written. It is Leela's biography as well. (Kottiswari, 2008, pp.,78-117).

The application of postmodernist critical techniques was more successful to ethical and social problems. For instance, the collapse of patriarchy and the women's defence against its dominance. The example of the combination of minimalist technique with a kind of postmodern 'retro' style. Through artists and the critical establishment, techniques of postmodernist art asked for interpretations that depended on theoretical notions such as reflexivity, as has been emerged out of the artist's self-consciousness. (Butler, 2002, pp.,85).

Conclusion

As it has been shown and explained, postmodernism is a literary movement that has been very active towards ethics and society issues. As a historical period, postmodernism implies certain ideas, cultural formations and styles. Postmodernism represents a rejection of the status of mimicry of the drama and as a result it attacks at the roots of representation of man's ideas and ideologies. The instability of the meaning exists in postmodern literature as well as an emphasis on the inadequate language that represents truth in a complete and an accurate manner. Although in some specific aspects of representation, there exists the break between postmodernism and modernism in such as its stand toward grand narratives. There still some aspects that postmodernism makes use of from modernism. The use of modern literary devices\techniques such as parody, pastiche, fragmentation and irony in postmodernist literary works. However, the employment of postmodernist techniques is slightly different from those found in modernism. Though the different use of techniques between postmodern and modern writers, they share common things. Therefore, the postmodern literature is characterized with ambiguity, complexity, and fragmented dialogue, use of black humor and, parody. The world represents a metaphor for the human status as it is seen to be unfriendly planet, but it can progress from fragmentation into

integration. The stream of consciousness, and the way of life is prevailing to bring back the narrow social and psychological steadiness of the society as a whole.

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Rgwan Abdalhameed Shuash

Language Academy, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia,
Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Malik OufiJasim Al-Maliki

Language Academy, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia,
Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Seriaznita Binti Said

Language Academy, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia,
Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Al-Fartoosi Rana Ali Mhoodar

Language Academy, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia,
Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
